

DEPARTMENT OF ARCHAEOLOGY
School for Archaeology, Geography and
Environmental Sciences
Whiteknights Campus
Reading, UK

2019
ARCHAEOLOGICAL EXCAVATIONS
IN DABARSKO POLJE –
Archaeological sites
HATELJI and MILAVIĆI (CRKVINA)

PRELIMINARY REPORT

Author: dr. Saša Čaval,
Marie Skłodowska-Curie Fellow

October 2019

PRESENTED RESEARCH IS PART OF THE PROJECT ‘**SOCIAL LANDSCAPES AS MULTICULTURAL SPACES: STEĆCI IN BOSNIA AND HERZEGOVINA**’ (SOLMUS), WHICH HAS RECEIVED FUNDING FROM THE EUROPEAN UNION’S HORIZON 2020 RESEARCH AND INNOVATION PROGRAMME UNDER THE MARIE SKŁODOWSKA-CURIE GRANT AGREEMENT NO. **797881**.

GENERAL

Archaeological excavations in the summer of 2019 were performed within SOLMUS project. The two main sites, identified after a scrupulous archaeological (Srdić 2019) and geophysical (Fry 2019) surveys on the territory of the medieval župa Dabar, ended up being a prehistoric mound with 13 medieval stećci monuments in the village of Hatelji, and a modern cemetery Milavići (k.o. Bijeljani, plot no. 674), with 354 medieval stećci monuments, locally known as Crkvine.

The excavations were performed in collaboration with the National institute for protection of historical, cultural and natural heritage (NIPHCHNH), Banja Luka, Republic of Srpska, Bosnia and Herzegovina, and their two archaeologists prof. Ljubica Srdić and Mrs. Ljiljana Vručinić.

The excavation was also a part of educational program of University of Reading, UK and Stanford University, USA, students and faculty of those, and other universities collaborated. The archaeological summer school attended undergraduate and graduate students of the following universities:

- University of Belgrade, Serbia (UoBel)
- Ca'Foscari University, Venice, Italy (Ca'Foscari)
- University of Ljubljana, Slovenia (UoLJ)
- University of Primorska, Koper, Slovenia (UoPri)
- University of Reading, UK (UoR)
- Stanford University, USA (Stanford)
- La Sapienza, Rome, Italy (Sapienza)

The scientific specialists and lecturers also came from the above universities, and likewise from the Institute of Archaeology, Scientific-Research Centre of the Slovenian Academy of Sciences and Arts (SRC SASA), Ljubljana, Slovenia.

The analyses will be performed in the institutions in the UK (osteology, isotopes, micromorphology, archaeobotany), BiH (genetics), Serbia (genetics), Slovenia (numismatics, ceramics, petrography), Spain (genetics), Belgium (archaeobotany).

The final number of the whole team stopped at 47 people.

HATELJI - PREHISTORIC BARROW WITH MEDIEVAL STEĆCI MONUMENTS

1. Introduction

Hatelji, a village in the municipality of Berkovići, Republika Srpska, BiH, is known to archaeological audience primarily for its cave site Hateljska pećina, high above the village and plane. Archaeological excavations that took place there in the 1980's revealed traces of habitation from the Neolithic and Eneolithic periods, early Bronze Age and the Middle Ages.¹

Hatelji: View of the barrow I. prior excavation.

¹ Cf. Marijanović, B. 2000, Contributions for the Prehistory of the Hinterland of the Adriatic Coast (Discussion D. Periša) – In: Arheološki vestnik 54 (2003), 431–438.

In the lowland, below the cliff with the cave, on the northern side of the central part of Dabarsko polje, lies a barrow burial ground with 5 tumuli, theoretically from the Middle Bronze Age.² At present two of them (barrow I and II) have the stone monuments – stećci placed on them. As part of the SOLMUS project, we began to investigate barrow I, which lies south of the Hatelji – Berkovići regional road, right next to the village. The mound is located in the plane of Dabarsko polje, which is used for cattle and sheep grazing. For the neighbouring shepherds this location is a popular place to meet and socialize during the daily pastoral breaks.

On this barrow, with a diameter of 20.5m, are 13 stećci monuments. Their placement did not significantly damage the prehistoric mound, since it is preserved up to 3m in height.³

Hatelji: View of the prehistoric barrows.

² In the 1980s a half of barrow V was excavated but there are no preserved documents on preformed survey. According to the testimony of the natives the archaeological researchers encountered in poorly preserved bone residues. See Čović, B. 1983, Istočna Hercegovina I zapadna Crna Gora. – In: Praistorija Jugoslavenskih zemalja IV, Bronzano doba, Sarajevo, 161–170.

The custom of the mound burial is also preserved within the Glasinac Culture, to which the surveyed area would belong during the Early Iron Age. See Čović B. 1987, Glasinačka kultura. – In: Praistorija Jugoslavenskih zemalja V, Željezno doba, Sarajevo, 575–643.

³ The mound is not situated on a completely flat area of the Dabar field. With a topographic survey it was undoubtedly estimated that the natural base is falling towards south, so we only give an estimate of the preserved height of the barrow.

2. Methodology

The scientific methodology for the excavation of Hatelji archaeological site was adopted from a prehistoric archaeology. The site directors were Dr Lucija Grahek (SRC SASA) and Dr Monika Milosavljević (UoBel).

The stratigraphic excavations were performed on a part of a prehistoric mound with stećci tombstones located in 3 rows over the mound.

The excavation area comprised of two large test trenches (TT1 and TT2 & TT2E), which included also 3 stećci monuments and possible burials underneath them.

The fieldwork documentation for this site is quite extent. We collected 58 samples for numerous analyses: (osteology, pathology, isotope studies, zooarchaeological, archaeobotanical, micromorphological, archaeometrical, petrographical, etc.)

3. Preliminary results

Archaeological research on the barrow I near Hatelji, on which at least 13 stećci monuments were placed, started with excavation of TT 1 and 2 (with an extension into Trench 2E). Although the excavation didn't reach the base of the mound, we did gain at least some insight into its structure. Findings of some more calcified bone fragments and some ceramic fragments indicate that this is undoubtedly a prehistoric mound with burials. They were apparently covered with earthen gravel, while the upper part of the mound was represented by a stone mantle composed of differently sized, uncut limestone pieces.

Preliminary results of the excavations show that the prehistoric mound was a burial site for a particular type of the population living in this area, that is for very young children. We discovered 9 single children burials, dug into a top of the prehistoric mound. Unfortunately, due to the lack of time, the excavations, which initially planned to excavate the whole prehistoric mound, to the bottom of it, were not finished and only medieval period of the barrow "occupation " was explored. Therefore, eight (8) burials were excavated, while the ninth was only documented and was visible in the western section of the TT2.

The TT1, was positioned in the N-S direction and ran over the two stećci. In this TT we discovered, that next to an adult burial with a stećak tombstone, was placed also a child burial, concluding that the two individuals were in a familial relationship, probably a parent and a child.

With the excavations on the barrow I. in the village of Hatelji, we obtained a lot of new information. The discovery of a relatively large number of children graves in the immediate vicinity of the stećci monuments raises many questions and offers numerous opportunities for various studies of social structure and burial customs in the early Middle Ages. However, this research project should necessary continue with further excavations, since suspected burials of adults under stećci tombstones were not researched yet. In order to reach the aim of the SOLMUS research project, this is to examine the continuity of the ritual site from prehistoric times to the Middle Ages,

we should also complete the excavation of the prehistoric mound, since we did not reach prehistoric burials in the first year of excavations.

Grave 2

MILAVIĆI – MEDIIEVAL STEĆCI CEMETERY WITH MODERN BURIALS

1. Introduction

Milavići cemetery is a communal cemetery in the municipality of Bileća, Republika Srpska, BiH. It supposedly serves the two nearby villages, Strupići and Kljenci.

The modern cemetery originates far back in the past. The central part of the cemetery is somewhat lifted, suggesting it developed from a prehistoric barrow. In the medieval period this cemetery was a final resting place for a larger community, as there are 352 stećci tombstones still preserved, along with a number of burials without such a marker but with a declared space in between the tombstones.

After initial surveys of the whole cemetery, of size 113m x 120m, we decided on two excavation areas within this site: the burial part with stećci tombstones in the SW corner of the cemetery, named area 1000, and another one on the elevated, central part of the cemetery, where the geophysical survey showed a possible built structure - area 2000. With this cemetery also bearing a toponym Crkvine, we reasonably anticipated to come across the remains of a medieval church.

2. Methodology

The main methodology in both areas was stratigraphic excavation, with smaller arbitrary excavations but only within the same stratigraphic unit (SU).

Area 1000: the eight (8) tombstones initially chosen to be excavated, were first cleaned of the vegetation to the level of exposed lower edges of the monuments. After that the tombstones were cleaned, only with water, pressure washer and brushes. Later the tombstones were photographed and documented. Each tombstone got a number and an SU number. Standard documentation forms were filled, describing the specifics of each monument and the photos for 3D modelling were taken. Subsequently, the monuments were moved from their original place to the field-road outside and next to the concrete and metal fence around the cemetery. However, due to the size, weight and vegetation “hug” of the tombstones, we could only move four (4) out of eight (8) tombstones, that is monuments no. 4 to 7.

At this point the second phase of the graves' excavation began. First, we documented everything as it was, and then, we proceeded with removing the fill of each separate grave.

Due to the sampling procedures for micromorphological analyses, we first excavated only bottom half of the grave, that is the leg areas. Afterwards we sampled the soil in the section as this allowed us to clearly see the borders between the grave fill and the virgin soil around it, and the limits between the fills.

MIL19: Area 1000: units 1-7. Only graves 4-7 were excavated. Drawing: L. Lewson.

In the next phase we fully excavated the graves, stopping only when reaching the stone cover of the burials. All four (4) excavated burials had a 'cover' of the grave cavity, made from natural rock plates – the so-called cyst type of grave. When removing those, the side structure and the skeletons were revealed. The 'walls' around the graves were of two different types: either similar plates, that served as the cover but bigger, were also placed around the grave, without any mortar between them, or the 'walls' were made from stone blocks, partially worked into the right shape, and had mortar to glue the stones together. All the burials were single, adult burials, with hardly any grave goods.

They were placed in grave in elongated positions, with their hands either by the body or on their laps. The graves didn't have similar, built bottoms, but the deceased were placed onto a ground.

MIL19: Area 2000

Area 2000: We situated the TTs within the empty area between tree-stumps and scattered tombstones. The test trench 1 (TT1) measured 3 x 4 m, and was placed on a part of a structure, found at the geophysical survey. During the excavations we decided to extend the TT for another 2 x 8 m, further to the west. During the excavations we came across a large amount of building material, from which we understood that we are at the location of a built structure, with stone blocks, mortar and ceramic roof tiles and bricks.

MIL19: Area 2000

At the depth of 70cm we reached a few mason structural stones, with one having a door hole in it. To our surprise, when excavating further, we did not reach a building's wall but two graves with a cist, where three individuals were buried. Both graves were covered with three large stone blocks, with smaller stones in-between.

MIL19: Area 2000

Inside the grave structures, the cists, were adult individuals. Grave 1 contained a full skeleton with white glazed majolica by the left leg's knee. The grave 2 contained two individuals. Individual 1 was an old lady without any grave goods, lying in an elongated position in the grave, while the individual no. 2 had their bones neatly placed by the lower part legs of an individual no.1. Only long bones and some ribs of the individual 2 from the grave 2 were preserved. It seems that whoever placed the bones back into the grave, did not include the skull and other parts of the skeleton.

3. Preliminary results

Area 1000: The excavated four graves gave us decent picture of the medieval burials in this cemetery. The grave goods were scarce. There was one coin found in the grave no. 4, placed in the right palm of the deceased. We took numerous samples to help us identify the burial custom in this community, however the results will be available only within a calendar year. The coin from the grave 04 was sent to Dr Andrej Šemrov, from the Numismatic cabinet in the National Museum of Slovenia, Ljubljana, Slovenia, for the conservation and analysis.

MIL19: Area 1000

Grave 04

Grave 05

Grave 06

Milavići, Area 1000, grave 7: a sketch of the grave cover and grave chamber with the skeleton (Author: Kaja Pavletič).

Area 2000: In this area the two graves we encountered did not have any grave goods but the majolica in grave 01. The numerous samples were taken, of which results will be available in a year's time. The skeletons will undergo an osteological and pathological analyses at the University of Reading.

Milavići, A2000: A white glazed majolica from the grave 1.

CONCLUSION

The archaeological excavations and research in Dabarsko polje, at the sites of Hatelji and Milavići proved to be a very successful season, which was intensely followed by local public. The excavations have not reached to geological level yet, thus the research will continue in June and July next year, following the same methodological approach and the structure of the team. The future workplan has already been presented to all the colleagues, and they all confirmed further collaboration.

As the PI of the project and the director of the archaeological excavations I would like to thank all the people involved into this research, but especially my Bosnian colleagues, Ljubica Srđić and Ljiljana Vrućinić. Without them our work in Dabar would not be possible and, in particular, would not be as successful.

HVALA LJUBICA I LJILJANA!